

Post operative ambulation on pain, analgesic usage, daily activities, length of stay, biological and physiological parameters among abdominal surgery patients: a cross sectional study

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Abstract

Introduction: Early ambulation is a technique in which the patients can move from the bed. Ambulation improves blood circulation, facilitates quicker wound healing and has a great impact on physical and psychological wellbeing. **Aim:** The aim is to determine the effectiveness of early ambulation on pain, analgesic usage, daily activity, length of hospital stay and bio-physiological parameters among the patients who underwent midline laparotomy. **Result:** A pre-and post-test control group design was used among 162 patients undergoing abdominal surgery. The patients were ambulated after 15 hours of post operative periods following surgery. The result revealed a statistically significant difference in pain level, daily activity, physiological parameters and reduced length of hospital stay between the groups ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** This indicates that the intervention helps to reduce post-operative pain, analgesic usage, improves daily activity, maintained stable physiological parameters and reduces the length of stay in the study group. It concluded that initiation of early ambulation in the immediate post-operative period improving the quality of selected post operative recovery among abdominal surgery patients.

Keywords: Early ambulation, Pain, daily activities, physiological parameters, abdominal surgery

INTRODUCTION

Early ambulation can have a great effect on the recovery process after abdominal surgery. Mobility improves blood circulation, quicker wound healing and has a great impact on mental and emotional health after surgery. Worldwide, more than 300 million surgical procedures are carried out per year, seven million postoperative complications in LMICs (Low- and middle-income countries) occur, 143 million additional surgical procedures are needed per year to save lives and prevent disability. By 2030, the majority of countries would reach 5000 surgical procedures per 100 000 population. The LMICs would take a huge burden and a loss in economic productivity, estimated at 12.3 trillion USD between 2015 to 2030 (1). The global survey of 2030, projected uniform progress in mortality and morbidity from common surgical conditions. The need for the surgical procedure would continue to rise substantially until 2030. Due to the absence of surgical interventions in many countries, case-fatality rates are high for common, easily treatable surgical conditions (2).

World Health Organization bulletin (2016), reported a rise of 266.2 to 359.5 million surgical operations from 2004 to 2012. The Lancet Commission on Global Surgery has projected that five billion people did not have adequate access to safe, surgical and anaesthesia care. In low- and middle-income countries, an additional one million emergency and essential operations are required. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank, have emphasized surgical care is an essential and central element for global health development (3). A national survey in the United States reported that surgery in the gastrointestinal system is one of the third most frequent operative procedures. Between 2003 and 2012, the largest increase rate (+10.9 % per annum) was observed on partial or complete gastrectomy, over 10 years, an increase in the post operative stay from 9.3 to 23.6 days per 100,000 population was reported (4,5).

Nurses play an active role in understanding patients' needs and concerns at various levels of pain from different aetiologies (6). A multimodal pain management is a modified approach that includes medications, early mobilization and nonpharmacologic therapies. Survey of surgical patients reported, 80 % of the patients prefer non-opioid medication for post operative pain and 94% of adults have chosen an alternative to opioids for surgical pain. Early mobility is the most important intervention linked to decreased morbidity and mortality related to surgical conditions (7). A pain scale is a valid and reliable scale to measure the intensity of pain after surgery. It is a self-reported scale that takes <1 minute to complete and is easy to interpret the score. (8).

BACK GROUND OF THE STUDY

Early Mobility, reduction of post-operative pain level, improved activities of daily living and quality of life are the predictive factor for the assessment of health outcomes after surgery. Patients admitted in the hospital often face difficulties with mobility and functionally decline, despite treating the acute illness. Transformation of dependency level to independence activity level will depend on the nurse's role. Experience of minimal or no pain, makes the patients to participate in normal activities. Nurses are in a position to measure the severity of post-operative pain and give care for early recovery. Early ambulation is a general nursing measure and an important post-operative intervention that reduces post- operative pain and improves daily activity level. (9,10)

A meta-analysis and systematic review showed a relationship between physical activity and hospital length of stay. Sitting position, early ambulation on the first and second post-operative day had shorter hospital stays. Post- operative patients who were inactive had significantly longer median length of stay (6 vs 5 days). A negative correlation is exhibited between the length of hospital stays and the walking distance indicating that early mobilization improves the optimal functional recovery (11). The impact of preoperative functional status upon ventral hernia repair was evaluated among 76,397 patients. The result revealed, that majority (97.9%) were independent, short-term outcomes like wound occurrence, pneumonia, pulmonary complications, urinary tract infection, cardiac complications, deep venous thrombosis, sepsis, re-admission and death were exposed to be a high risk for postoperative complications. (12)

Studies indicate that early ambulation, crucial for post-operative recovery, is frequently delayed, with up to 88% of patients spending the majority of their time in bed after surgery. Particularly after midline laparotomy, patients face challenges such as substantial blood loss, large incisions, and reliance on drains and catheters, leading to functional impairment and severe pain. To enhance recovery, non-pharmacological interventions like abdominal binders and early ambulation are essential. However,

research in India on the impact of early ambulation on pain management, analgesic usage, and recovery parameters among midline laparotomy patients remains limited. Investigating the effectiveness of scheduled early ambulation could significantly improve post-operative outcomes in abdominal surgery patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was approved by General Hospital Institution Ethical Committee from Government of Pondicherry. All participants were informed about the study and obtained consent by translating in the local language. The participants were assessed for level of pain, activity of daily living and length of hospital stay from the day of admission to the post operative ward and till discharge from hospital. A quantitative approach - an experimental design design- Pre and Post-test with control group design and repeated measures analysis was used among 162 laparotomy patients

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Group	Pre test After 15 hours of post-operative period	Intervention	Post- test							
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Control group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collected demographic variables (prior surgery) Level of pain, Analgesic requirements Daily activity Physiological and Biochemical parameters (prior surgery) Length of pre hospital stay 	Routine Hospital care (Ambulation after 24 hours)	After every 24 hours of intervention, the post test was assessed for, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pain, Number of analgesics used Activities of daily living Length of stay Physiological parameters Biochemical parameters (post –test 2 and 6) for seven continuous days and on discharge. Follow up done for 30 days following surgery.							
Experimental group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collected demographic variables Level of pain, Analgesic requirements Daily activity Physiological and Biochemical parameters (prior surgery) Length of pre hospital stay 	After 15 hours of post operative period, following surgery initiated early ambulation twice a day, 50 feet on first post-operative period, thereafter encouraged to increase the step count of 10 feet throughout the post-operative days till discharge.	After every 24 hours of intervention, the post test was assessed for, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pain, Number of analgesics used Activities of daily living Length of stay Physiological parameters Biochemical parameters (post –test 2 and 6) for seven continuous days and on discharge. Follow up done for 30 days following surgery.							

STATISTICAL METHODS:

The study employed descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics described demographic variables, while chi-square tests assessed associations. Pain levels, analgesic usage, and daily activity were analyzed using Friedman repeated measure ANOVA with Dunnett’s test. Bio-physiological parameters underwent two-way RM ANOVA with Bonferroni t-tests for multiple comparisons. A significance threshold of 0.05 or less was used for pain and activity analyses, and 0.001 or less for bio-physiological parameters. Sigma Plot 13 (Systat Software Inc., USA) facilitated analysis and graph plotting.

RESULTS

Level of pain: In Figure 1, the control group exhibited median pain scores of 8, 7, 7, 6, 5, 5, 4, 4, and 0 for pre-test and post-tests 1 through 8, respectively, with a significant difference ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, the experimental group displayed median pain scores of 8, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, and 0 for the same tests, also showing a significant difference ($p < 0.001$). The pre-test comparison between control and experimental groups was not statistically significant ($p = 0.931$). However, post-tests 1, 2, and 3 showed statistically significant differences between the control and experimental groups ($p < 0.001$). Notably, the experimental group exhibited a notable reduction in pain scores from post-test 2 to post-test 3. Further, post-tests 4 through 7 also showed significant differences between the control and experimental groups ($p < 0.001$). Finally, post-test 8 demonstrated a significant difference ($p = 0.001$), indicating that early ambulation effectively reduced pain scores among patients undergoing abdominal surgery.

Number of analgesic usage: The analgesic medications were grouped into three categories: 0 or 1, 2 or 3, and 4 and above. Pre-test comparisons between the control and experimental groups showed no statistically significant difference ($P = 0.875$). However, on post-test 1, the control group exhibited numbers of 0, 63, and 18, significantly different from the experimental group's numbers of 26, 55, and 0 ($P < 0.001$). Similarly, on post-test 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7, the control group's numbers were significantly different from the experimental group's ($P < 0.001$). Notably, on post-test 8, there was no statistically significant difference between the control and experimental groups ($P = 1$), indicating the effectiveness of early ambulation in reducing the need for analgesic medications after abdominal surgery.

Figure 1: Comparison of pain in control and experimental groups.

Table 1: Comparison of analgesic usage						
S.No.	Duration	Groups	0 or 1	2 or 3	4 and above	Statistical Analysis
1	Pre-test	Control	0	41	40	$\chi^2 = 0.0247$ P = 0.875
		Experimental	0	41	40	
	Post-test 1	Control	0	63	18	$\chi^2 = 44.542$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	26	55	0	
	Post-test 2	Control	0	78	3	$\chi^2 = 162.000$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	81	0	0	
	Post-test 3	Control	11	67	3	$\chi^2 = 123.261$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	81	0	0	
	Post-test 4	Control	12	66	3	$\chi^2 = 120.194$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	81	0	0	
	Post-test 5	Control	34	47	0	$\chi^2 = 63.421$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	81	0	0	
	Post-test 6	Control	40	41	0	$\chi^2 = 52.248$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	81	0	0	
	Post-test 7	Control	48	33	0	$\chi^2 = 38.968$ P < 0.001
		Experimental	81	0	0	
	Post-test 8	Control	81	0	0	$\chi^2 = 0$ P = 1
		Experimental	81	0	0	
Table 1. shows the Analgesic usage in control and experimental group.						

Overall Activities of daily living: Figure 2 shows the median of control pre-test and post-test 1, post-test 2, post-test 3, post-test 4, post-test 5, post-test 6, post-test 7 and post-test 8 were 0,0,5, 18, 32, 42, 52, 73 and 95. There was a statistically significant difference in the control group (p < 0.001). The median of experimental group pre-test and post-test 1, post-test 2, post-test 3, post-test 4, post-test 5, post-test 6, post-test 7 and post-test 8 were 0, 22, 51, 75, 97, 100, 100, 100 and 100 respectively. There was a statistically significant difference in experimental group (p < 0.001). Figure 2 shows the control and experimental group activity score shows on comparison using Mann- Whitney rank sum test, the pre-test was not statistically significant (p = 1). The control post-test 1 activities of the daily living score were statistically significant from the experimental post-test 1 score (p < 0.001). The control post-test 2, 3, 4 and 5 activities of daily living score were statistically significant from the experimental post-test 2, 3, 4 and 5 score (p<0.001). In experimental group, there was a greater improvement from post-test 5 score from post-test 4 score which indicated that the experimental group was independent earlier than the control group participants. The control post-test 6, 7 and 8 activities of the daily living score were statistically significant from the experimental post-test 6, 7 and 8 score (p < 0.001), which showed that early ambulation is effective in improving the level of activities of daily living among patients who underwent abdominal surgery.

Figure 2: Comparison of activities of daily living (overall) total score in early ambulation procedure of control and experimental groups.

Figure 3: Comparison effect of pre-operative and post-operative length of hospital stay among the male and female patients undergone abdominal surgery

Table 2. Comparison of pre-operative and post-operative length of hospital stay among control and experimental patients undergone abdominal surgery (n = 162)					
S.No.	Parameter	Gender	Groups	Median	Percentile 25 – 75)
1	Length of hospital stay Pre-operation	Male	Con	4	4 – 5
			Exp	4	4 – 5
		Female	Con	5	4 – 5
			Exp	4	4 – 5
	Length of hospital stay Post-operation	Male	Con	11	10 – 11
			Exp	9	9 – 9
Female		Con	11	10 – 11	
		Exp	9	8.25 – 9	
n – Male – Control = 42; Experimental = 49 Female – Control = 39; Experimental = 32					
Table 2. Comparison effect of pre-operative and post-operative length of hospital stay among control and experimental patients undergone abdominal surgery.					

Length of hospital stay: Table 2 and Figure 3 present median, 25th percentile, and 75th percentile data on hospital stay length for both control and experimental groups. Given the ranked and discrete nature of the data, non-parametric statistics (Mann-Whitney rank sum test) were employed. mPre-operative length of hospital stay showed no significant difference between control and experimental groups for males ($p = 0.162$), but a significant difference for females ($p = 0.002$), with experimental group median being 4 and 5 respectively. Post-operatively, both male and female experimental groups had significantly shorter hospital stays compared to controls ($p < 0.002$). Figure 6 illustrates this difference, with a significant p-value ($p < 0.001$), indicating the efficacy of early ambulation in reducing hospital stay after abdominal surgery.

Physiological parameters:

Systolic blood pressure: Figure 4 illustrates the comparison of physiological parameters of systolic blood pressure related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post-operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The systolic blood pressure mean value of control group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 9 are 120.915,123.593, 123.358, 123.926, 119.704, 124.753, 120.963, 118.420, 119.284 and 119.062 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8and 9 are 119.062, 127.679, 127.679, 122.123, 124.173, 121.802, 121.037, 121.062, 120.642 and 121.086 respectively. The p value of pre- post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the experimental group shows stable physiological parameter of systolic blood pressure on the following post-operative days of 1 to 9 than the control group participants ($p= 0.074$) respectively .

Diastolic blood pressure: : Figure 5 illustrates comparison of physiological parameters of diastolic blood pressure related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post-operative patients between control and

experimental group in pre- post test. The diastolic blood pressure mean value of control group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 9 are 80.914, 87.160, 76.370, 76.494, 84.025, 78.062, 78.420, 75.975, 75.037 and 74.519 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8and 9 are 80.667, 81.827, 78.617, 80.691, 79.975, 79.432, 79.160, 79.062, 79.407 and 79.630 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the experimental group shows stable physiological parameter of diastolic blood pressure on the following post-operative days of 1 to 9 than the control group participants ($p= 0.005$) respectively

Pulse rate: The comparison of physiological parameters of pulse rate related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post- operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The mean value of control group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 9 are 84.321, 92.172, 82.444, 80.395, 79.506, 79.086, 80.049, 80.728, 82.790 and 81.556 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 9 are 77.975, 92.988, 99.136, 86.173, 79.309, 75.778, 74.963, 74.543, 73.136 and 72.123 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the experimental group shows stable physiological parameter of pulse rate on the following post-operative days of 1 to 9 than the control group participants ($p < 0.001$) respectively

Figure 4: Comparison of systolic blood pressure (SBP) in control and experimental groups.

Figure 5 Comparison of Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) in control and experimental groups.

Respiratory rate: The comparison of physiological parameters of respiratory rate related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post-operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The mean value of control group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 9 are 16.296, 19.284, 17.975, 16.889, 16.173, 15.383, 16.099, 13.926, 15.901 and 15.679 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 9 are 13.111, 16.716, 15.556, 19.728, 17.728, 18.000, 17.432, 15.753, 17.259 and 16.247 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the experimental group shows stable physiological parameter of Respiratory rate on the following post-operative days of 1 to 9 than the control group participants ($p < 0.001$) respectively

Bio- chemical parameters: The comparison of bio- chemical parameters like blood sugar, serum bilirubin , blood urea, aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post-operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. In blood sugar, the mean value of control group pre - post test 1 and 2 are 108. 012, 110.753 and 106.642 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1 and 2 are 109.457, 107.877 and 102.617 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the blood sugar shows statistically significant difference in post test 1 and 2 ($p = 0.029$) respectively (figure 8. 5). So early ambulation was an effective intervention to maintain stable bio - chemical parameter after abdominal surgery.

Bio- chemical parameters (serum bilirubin): The comparison of bio- chemical parameters of Sr. bilirubin related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post- operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The mean value of control group pre - post test 1 and 2 are 0.585, 0.543 and 0.531 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1 and 2 are 0.599, 0.357 and 0.412 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the sr. bilirubin shows statistically significant difference in post test 1 and 2 ($p < 0.001$) respectively So early ambulation was an effective intervention to maintain stable bio - chemical parameters after abdominal surgery.

Bio- chemical parameters (Blood urea): The comparison of bio- chemical parameters of Blood urea related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post- operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The mean value of control group pre - post test 1 and 2 are 14.457, 16.667 and 15.963 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1 and 2 are 14.272, 15.420 and 14.605 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group are $p < 0.001$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the blood urea shows statistically significant difference in post test 1 and 2 ($p < 0.001$) respectively (Figure 10). So early ambulation was an effective intervention to maintain stable bio - chemical parameters after abdominal surgery.

Bio- chemical parameters (aspartate aminotransferase (AST): The comparison of bio- chemical parameters of Aspartate amino transferase (AST) related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post- operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The mean value of control group pre - post test 1 and 2 are 24.259, 25.765 and 26.543 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1 and 2 are 22.901, 25. 370 and 23.272 respectively. The p value of pre - post within the group ($p = 0.034$), which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the aspartate amino transferase (AST) shows statistically significant difference in post test 2 ($p = 0.014$) respectively. So early ambulation was an effective intervention to maintain stable bio - chemical parameters after abdominal surgery.

Bio- chemical parameters (alanine aminotransferase (ALT): The comparison of bio- chemical parameters of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) related to effectiveness of early ambulation among post- operative patients between control and experimental group in pre- post test. The mean value of control group pre - post test 1 and 2 are 25.062, 24.469 and 25.309 respectively. The mean value of experimental group pre- post test 1 and 2 are 24.877, 23.148 and 20.617 respectively . The p value of pre - post within the group are $p = 0.017$, which shows statistically significant. On comparison, the Alanine amino transferase (ALT) shows statistically significant difference in post test 2 ($p, 0.001$) respectively. So early ambulation was an effective intervention to maintain stable bio - chemical parameters after abdominal surgery.

Discussion

Incision of the abdominal wall will stimulate the nerve fibers to trigger pain. (15). The present study shows there was a statistically significant difference in the median values of pain score and analgesic usage between pre-test and post-test in the control and experimental group. However, the study results showed greater reduction of pain scores in experimental groups than control group. Furthermore, the pre-test showed that there were no statistically significant difference between control and experimental groups. Whereas the difference in post-test 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 between control and experimental groups were greater than the expected by chance. However, In the experimental group, there was a greater improvement in post-test 3 scores which is indicating the reduction of pain score in the earlier phase. The study result showed that, early ambulation was most effective in reducing post-operative pain among the participants undergone abdominal surgery.

The study result was supported by Ni et al, (2018). A prospective randomized controlled trial investigated the effects of early enforced mobilization after liver resection on postoperative recovery among 120 patients. The results showed statistically significant difference in pain level, functional recovery time, first flatus time and shorter hospital stays in the experimental group. Early ambulation after liver resection reduced post-operative pain, economic burden, increased comfort, reduced nursing workload, rapid recovery, and patient satisfaction in the experimental group (16). The findings of the present study correspond with the study conducted by Ma et al, (2020). The study result showed that, after surgery, the administration of opioids to manage post-operative pain results in increased risk of opioid dependency and delay in discharge. Early postoperative ambulation was encouraged within 3 hours of operation among 1340 lower gastrointestinal surgery patients, which proved decreased postoperative pain, physiologic stress, and length of stay (17).

The study demonstrated that early ambulation effectively reduced analgesic usage among abdominal surgery patients. While pre-test values were similar between groups, post-tests showed significant reductions in analgesic usage in the experimental group compared to controls. This highlights the efficacy of early ambulation in post-operative pain management.

Early mobilization is an important element of postoperative care. Catabolism, endothelial dysfunction, fatigue, gastrointestinal dysfunction, hypoxic stress, and inflammation-mediated dysfunction occurs after surgery. Prevention of complications and early recovery can be achieved through early ambulation (Foss and Kehlet et al, 2020) (22).

The study was supported by the single-blind, parallel-arm, randomized trial that assessed the efficacy, feasibility and safety of a supervised postoperative exercise program among 108 major abdominal oncology surgical patients (24). The result showed, an early postoperative mobilization programme is safe, feasible, early discharge and improves functional capacity in major elective abdominal surgery patients (Almeida et al, 2017)

The study implemented early ambulation within 15 hours post-surgery, covering a distance of 50 feet twice daily until discharge. Compared to the control group, the experimental group demonstrated

significantly higher scores in overall daily activity, physical activity, physiological activity, and personal activity. Notably, post-test 5 scores in the experimental group significantly surpassed those of the control group ($p < 0.001$), indicating the effectiveness of early ambulation in enhancing activities of daily living after abdominal surgery. While challenges persist in pain management and achieving independence in daily activities post-operatively, early ambulation shows promise in reducing pain, improving activity levels, and shortening hospital stays for abdominal surgery patients. This highlights the importance for post-operative nurses to explore both pharmacological and non-pharmacological strategies to enhance post-operative recovery.

The study assessed physiological parameters (Systolic blood pressure, Diastolic blood pressure, Pulse rate, and Respiratory rate) before and after surgery. The experimental group, ambulated daily post-surgery, showed more stable physiological parameters compared to the control group. Biochemical parameters (Blood sugar, Blood urea, Serum bilirubin, Aspartate amino-transferase, and Alanine amino-transferase) were also measured. Early ambulation maintained normal biochemical parameters better in the experimental group compared to the control group. These findings highlight the effectiveness of early ambulation in maintaining stable physiological and biochemical parameters post-abdominal surgery.

Summary and conclusion

Nursing is a service-oriented profession that focuses on health promotion and it is the most significant general nursing measure. Nurses had higher perceived barriers (lack of training and comfort) to mobilizing hospitalized patients and considered patient mobilization will be an additional workload for nurses. So, nurses need updated knowledge on the importance of ambulating post-operative patients after abdominal surgery. The nurse educator plays a significant role in educating, imparting knowledge and collaborating with other health care team members about the development of a strict schedule which can positively impact nurses' understanding related to the risks of immobility, benefits of early mobility and prevention of post-operative complications. So awareness and education to be given among pre-operative patients and patients relatives about the importance of early ambulation after surgery for early and quality of post-operative recovery.

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